

A Spiritual Phenomenology of Miniature Spaces: Reading Gaston Bachelard's *The Poetics of Space*

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Prelude: Gaston Bachelard and the Genesis of *The Poetics of Space*

Gaston Bachelard (1884–1962) was a French philosopher whose intellectual journey led him from the sciences to poetics, and from epistemology to a deeply introspective phenomenology of the imagination. His early academic career was rooted in the philosophy of science, in which he made significant contributions to the understanding of scientific knowledge, discontinuity, and epistemological rupture. In the 1940s, however, Bachelard's focus shifted toward a different kind of knowing, not analytic or empirical, but intuitive, poetic, intimate.¹ *The Poetics of Space* (*La poétique de l'espace*) was published in 1957 near the end of Bachelard's life. It stands as one of his most enduring and widely read works, partly because it marks a decisive turn away from scientific thought to phenomenological reflection. Bachelard does not analyse space as a geometric or physical category, but as something deeply lived and experienced, especially through poetic imagery.² His core concern is how the imagination inhabits space, the becoming of houses, rooms, corners, drawers, and nests into

1 Some works of note include: Gaston Bachelard, *La psychanalyse du feu*, Paris: Gallimard, 1938; *La philosophie du non: Essai d'une philosophie du nouvel esprit scientifique*, Paris: PUF, 1940; *L'eau et les rêves: Essai sur l'imagination de la matière*, Paris: José Corti, 1941; *L'air et les songes: Essai sur l'imagination du mouvement*, Paris: José Corti, 1943; *La terre et les rêveries de la volonté*, Paris: José Corti, 1948; *La poétique de l'espace*, Paris: PUF, 1957; *La poétique de la rêverie*, Paris: PUF, 1960; *La flamme d'une chandelle*, Paris: PUF, 1961; *Le droit de rêver*, Paris: PUF, 1970 (published posthumously).

2 Robert Vigneault, "Bachelard, Gaston," in Irena R. Makaryk (ed.), *Encyclopedia of Contemporary Literary Theory: Approaches, Scholars, Terms* (Toronto, University of Toronto Press, 2000), 239–241.

zones of being. Charged with memory and reverie, they invoke “a feeling of participation in a flowing onward, necessarily expressed in terms of time and secondarily expressed in terms of space.”³

The postwar intellectual climate in France was ripe for this shift. In the 1950s, French thought grappled with the aftermath of existentialism, the rise of structuralism, and the lingering trauma of war.⁴ Against this backdrop, Bachelard’s focus on the interior, the intimate, and the contemplative offered an alternative to the sociopolitical urgency that characterised much of mid-century philosophy. In this light, Bachelard’s later work can be read as a quiet counter-current, a return to the personal and elemental. Bachelard’s own life gave him a particular sensitivity to domestic and miniature spaces. Born in the small town of Bar-sur-Aube in the Champagne region, he was the son of a shoemaker and spent his early years in modest surroundings. He later recalled how everyday objects such as drawers, attics, and quiet rooms were the ground of his early imaginative life. In his turn toward phenomenology, these seemingly insignificant objects and ‘corners’ of everyday life established Bachelard’s intellectual reflection in the material and emotional textures of ordinary life.

Why Read Bachelard Spiritually?

In *The Poetics of Space*, Bachelard invites us to go beyond detached observation of the world and to inhabit it intimately. Drawing on poets and writers such

3 Gaston Bachelard, *The Poetics of Space*, trans. Maria Jolas, forew. John R. Stilgoe (Boston, MA: Beacon Press, 1994), xvi. For further reading on the correlation between mysticism, space and spatiality, see Carmel Bendon Davis, *Mysticism & Space: Space and Spatiality in the Works of Richard Rolle, The Cloud of Unknowing Author and Julian of Norwich* (Washington, D.C.: The Catholic University of America Press, 2008), 1–13.

4 By the mid-1950s, French intellectual life was marked by a period of transition. Postwar existentialism, associated with figures such as Jean-Paul Sartre and Albert Camus, had highlighted questions of freedom, anguish, and responsibility in response to the moral and existential trauma of World War II. At the same time, new currents of thought were emerging that shifted attention away from subjective experience toward impersonal structures of meaning, particularly in language, anthropology, and culture (later grouped under the term *Structuralism*). Within this context of philosophical fatigue with abstraction on the one hand and existential crisis on the other, Bachelard’s turn toward imagination, interiority, and lived space was not escapism. It was a different way of being serious: a commitment to the small, the quiet, and the interior, in a culture still echoing with bombings and betrayal. Bachelard offered healing through intimacy, not confrontation. See: Roch C. Smith, *Gaston Bachelard: Philosopher of Science and Imagination* (Albany, NY: State University of New York Press, 2016), 1–8.

as Baudelaire, Rilke, Supervielle, and others, Bachelard explores how certain images of space activate what he calls “reverberations” in “the most profound depths of its being.”⁵ *The Poetics of Space* does not proceed through systematic argument but through phenomenological meditation, inviting the reader not to think about space but to dwell within it, that is, to remember, imagine, and inhabit the small. His phenomenology of the house, of corners and chests, of nests and drawers, has long served poets, philosophers, and architects as a guide to lived space. Yet what if we read Bachelard not only as a philosopher of poetics but as an inadvertent spiritual guide? What if we considered that his meditations on miniature spaces might already be theological in their reverence, contemplative in their slowness, and mystical in their reach?

This paper proposes such a reading. It does not claim that Bachelard was a theologian or that he intended to formulate a spiritual phenomenology. Rather, it suggests that Bachelard’s account of miniature spaces – those intimate, condensed forms of being – resonates deeply with the structures of mystical and contemplative life. The chest, the shell, the corner, the dollhouse: each image offers itself to the imagination in ways that mimic the dynamics of spiritual attention. In Bachelard’s reveries, we are invited to enter space carefully and be still, that we may encounter the infinite folded into the finite. Seen in this light, reading Bachelard spiritually is not about forcefully theologising *The Poetics of Space*, but about listening to it with a contemplative ear. His phenomenology does not just describe objects; it “awakens”⁶ them. In doing so, it awakens the reader to a quality of attention that borders on prayer. The act of lingering with a miniature, of holding its silence, and allowing it to speak (or to ‘reverberate’ in Bachelard’s language) is remarkably close to the contemplative practices found across mystical traditions. The inward movement Bachelard describes from the outer immensity of the world to the “immensity within”⁷ is not unlike the inward turn practised by mystics across different traditions.

What emerges from this way of reading is a spiritual phenomenology of miniature spaces, that is, a mode of presence rooted in attention and interiority, a taking in of the paradoxical vastness of the small. This reading is neither apologetic nor exegetical; rather, it is phenomenological in Bachelard’s spirit because it neither explains nor argues. Instead, it dwells, ruminates, or reveries.

5 Bachelard, *The Poetics of Space*, xvii.

6 Bachelard, *The Poetics of Space*, xxiii.

7 Bachelard, *The Poetics of Space*, xxxix, see also 184.

As we follow his meditations on the miniature, we repeatedly find ourselves at the threshold of the sacred, not grandiose or dogmatic but small and hidden, the dwelling kind of the cloister, the womb, the hazelnut. In what follows, we explore how Bachelard's language of contraction, intimacy, and reverie lends itself quite naturally to spiritual reflection. We begin with his phenomenology of miniature space, showing how the small becomes the site of ontological richness. We then explore the resonance of this framework with the interior spiritual life, and how the inward turn is also a turn towards presence. From there, we move to Bachelard's treatment of immensity, which paradoxically emerges from the most intimate spaces, and draw on spiritual traditions that have long known the infinite to dwell in the finite. We end by proposing a spiritual phenomenology of space, one attentive to stillness, depth, and the imaginative inhabitation of being.

Miniature as Spiritual *Topos*: From Reverie to Presence

For Bachelard, the miniature is not a diminished object but an ontological concentration. It is a site of reverie, a *topos* in the ancient sense, that is, a place that holds being, "the first unchangeable limit of that which surrounds," and, by extension, thought.⁸ What may be small, hidden or folded, is not reduced for Bachelard, but intensified. The miniature gathers a presence that exceeds its dimensions. It becomes a threshold, a liminal space between perception and imagination, between object and interiority. It is this threshold quality that lends the miniature its spiritual valence. We often associate spiritual space with expansive spaces such as a cathedral or a mountaintop. Yet Bachelard invites us to reverse this intuition, drawing our gaze to the drawer, the shell, the nut, or the child's toy chest. These are not merely containers; they are what he calls 'zones of being.'⁹ In them, the soul can nest and inhabit inwardly. And that act of inhabitation, for Bachelard, is not primarily intellectual, but affective and intuitive, almost devotional in quality, a mode of reverie. Reverie, unlike fantasy or escapism, is a serious form of attention. Bachelard does not see it as projecting a wishful thought, but as a dwelling-with, a resting-in. The miniature holds our gaze not because it is useful or explanatory but because

8 Aristotle, *Physics: Books III and IV*, IV.4, 212a2-30, trans. Edward Hussey, Clarendon Aristotle Series (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1993), 28-29.

9 Bachelard, *The Poetics of Space*, 222.

it invites a contemplative presence, a type of attention that resists analysis.¹⁰ It cannot be rushed or mastered. Instead, it lets the object reverberate in the consciousness of the one who looks. This resonance – silent, slow, and deep – is, in mystical jargon, contemplation.¹¹ Therefore, the implicit spirituality in Bachelard’s method is unmistakable. He does not speak in theological terms, but the structure of his phenomenology parallels the time-honoured mystical practice of attending to the near, the hidden, the small, the now and finding there the presence of something infinite. The miniature concentrates the world. Its smallness is curiously a spiritual mass. In this way, Bachelard’s thought echoes the paradox at the heart of contemplative spirituality: the infinite dwells in the finite and, more still, it often hides itself there, awaiting a certain gaze.

An illustrative example is Julian of Norwich’s vision in the First Revelation of “something small, no bigger than a hazelnut, lying in the palm of my hand” as a theological miniature. Amazed that despite its littleness, the hazelnut will not perish into nothingness, she exclaims, “It lasts, and ever will, because God loves

10 Likewise, Simone Weil famously described attention as the purest and most selfless act the soul can perform, calling it “the rarest and purest form of generosity.” In her essay “Reflections on the Right Use of School Studies with a View to the Love of God,” she writes that “prayer consists of attention” and that real attention involves waiting in silence, not striving to grasp or master what is before us, but allowing it to reveal itself on its own terms. This form of attention contrasts sharply with the analytical impulse to manipulate the object, that is, to interrogate it, define it, dissect it, reduce it to a function or category. For Weil, as for Bachelard, such manipulation violates the object’s integrity and disrupts the possibility of encounter. True attention, by contrast, is receptive rather than possessive. It is an orientation of loving availability, of offering space for what is other to emerge. In this way, Bachelard’s reverie, like Weil’s attention, does not seek to explain or control, but to dwell with, to be transformed by what is contemplated. Simone Weil, *Waiting for God*, trans. Emma Craufurd, intro. Leslie A. Fiedler (New York, NY: Harper & Row, 1973), 105–116.

11 For instance, in the Upanishads, the highest reality – *Brahman*, or the Self (*Atman*) – is revealed not through power, concept, form, or appearance, but in terms of subtlety, stillness, and interior presence. The *Svetasvatara Upanishad* describes the Self as that “than whom there is naught else higher, than whom there is naught smaller, naught greater” (3.9), that “who dwells in the heart of all things” (3.11). Similarly, the *Mundaka Upanishad* names the “flaming,” “imperishable” and “real” Brahman, “subtler than the subtle” (2.2). These verses suggest that divine presence is not absent but too subtle to be grasped and, hence, it must be received in stillness. *The Thirteen Principal Upanishads*, annot. Robert Ernest Hume (London: Oxford University Press, 1951), 372, 400–401. As Berta Dandler notes, the Upanishads speak of Brahman as being “beyond the range of human thought, and can only be apprehended through the awakening of a higher faculty of Self-knowledge which comes to light in a condition of inner stillness, brought about through the dedicated pursuit and practice of the spiritual life.” In this vision, contemplation is not a self-ascent to power or assertion, but an act of attentive interior dwelling through which the Real quietly resonates within. Berta Dandler, *Living Beyond Fear: Self-Knowledge in the Light of the Non-Dual Teachings* (London: Shanti Sadan, 2016), ch. 15.

it.”¹² It is precisely the kind of object Bachelard might linger over: tiny, held in the palm, and containing the world. He would not name it divine, but would perceive its capacity to contain immensity in intimacy. Thus, the hazelnut, like the drawer or the shell, becomes a site where being folds in on itself and the cosmos is gathered into a grain.

Importantly, Bachelard resists treating the miniature as a symbol. His phenomenology is not semiotic, for he does not ask what a shell means, but what kind of being it makes possible. His attention does not analyse but contemplates, thereby positioning his work as a powerful resource for spiritual reflection. For if theology is not always about propositions but sometimes about dwelling, if it is sometimes about staying with a space, attending to a presence, and allowing an image to form interiorly, then Bachelard becomes a fellow traveller on that contemplative itinerary. To enter a miniature, in Bachelard’s sense, is to allow the world to become close again. It is to retreat from the abstract scale or the utilitarian gaze to recover the nearness of things. The miniature does not overwhelm the senses, but beckons them inward. It invites the observant to listen, slow down, and become reverent. It draws the spiritual imagination not upward or outward but inward and downward, to what is protected and hidden away. In this way, miniature spaces become spiritual *topoi*, existential shelters where presence dwells and reveals itself. They are sites of intimacy and, in that intimacy, of immensity. To read Bachelard spiritually is to recognise that these spaces do not merely house things; they house presence. They gather silence. They welcome stillness. They call the soul to attention.

The Soul’s Dwelling: Interior Spaces and the Inward Turn

To understand space spiritually, we must think from the inside out. Space is not, at the outset, external or measurable, but lived in or dreamed about, interiorised even. His phenomenology resists the Cartesian abstraction of space as emptiness. Instead, he reintroduces us to space as a dwelling, a *milieu* of intimacy, memory, and being.¹³ This understanding prepares the ground for

12 Julian of Norwich, *Showings*, trans. Edmund Colledge and James Walsh, Classics of Western Spirituality Series (New York, NY: Paulist Press, 1978), 130 (short text), 183 (long text).

13 “And this is how a poet poses the phenomenological problem of the soul in all clarity. Pierre-Jean Jouve writes: ‘Poetry is a soul inaugurating a form.’ The soul inaugurates. Here it is the supreme power. It is human dignity. Even if the ‘form’ was already well-known, previously discovered, carved from ‘commonplaces,’ before the interior poetic light was turned upon it, it was a mere object for the mind. *But the soul comes and inaugurates the form, dwells in it, takes pleasure in it.* Pierre-Jean Jouve’s

a spiritual resonance, since the human soul is also a space. It is not a void, but a dwelling, a Teresian castle, a Mechthildian cloister, an Upanishadic flame, a Sufi mirror or a Buddhist lotus flower. And like the miniature spaces Bachelard reveres, the soul is not expansive in volume but in depth.

In *The Poetics of Space*, Bachelard explores various “houses” and “rooms” within the self. Drawers, trunks, and secret rooms represent a form of interiority that is not merely hidden or closed off but layered and “abided” in.¹⁴ The secret space is where the self retreats to “listen,”¹⁵ “remember,”¹⁶ and “dream.”¹⁷ The affective charge of such spaces is enormous: they are where we are most ourselves, where we discover who we are. These are spaces for repose rather than performance. They are not merely private; they are contemplative.

Mystical theology has long understood the soul in similar architectural terms. The most immediate parallel is Teresa of Ávila’s *Interior Castle*, in which the soul is described as a luminous structure composed of multiple “mansions” or chambers. One moves inward through the layers of this dwelling, each room drawing the soul closer to the divine presence in the central inner chamber. For Teresa, this movement is both metaphorical and ontological, marking the soul’s transformation through prayer.¹⁸ Likewise, Bachelard’s reverie on small spaces is not merely aesthetic appreciation. It is an ontological inhabitation in which the

statement can therefore be taken as a clear maxim of a phenomenology of the soul.” Bachelard, *The Poetics of Space*, xxii (emphasis ours).

14 Bachelard, *The Poetics of Space*, xxxvii.

15 Bachelard, *The Poetics of Space*, 13, 20, 31, 60, 66, 89, 124, 144, 166, 177–182, 215.

16 Bachelard, *The Poetics of Space*, xxxvii, 25, 32, 56, 79, 137, 142.

17 Bachelard, *The Poetics of Space*, xx, xxi, xxxvii, xxxviii, 3–18, 20–37, 39, 47–59, 61–66, 83–84, 98–104.

18 For Teresa of Avila, prayer does not merely console or instruct, but transforms the soul’s very substance and orientation, “Without any labour of one’s own, the temple of which I spoke is reared for the soul in which to pray: the senses and exterior surroundings appear to lose their hold, while the spirit gradually regains its lost sovereignty. Some say the soul enters into itself; others, that it rises above itself [...] Let us imagine that the senses and powers of the soul (which I compared in my allegory to the inhabitants of the castle) have fled and joined the enemy outside. After long days and years of absence, perceiving how great has been their loss, they return to the neighbourhood of the castle, but cannot manage to re-enter it, for their evil habits are hard to break off; still, they are no longer traitors, and they wander about outside. The King, Who holds His court within it, sees their good will, and out of His great mercy desires them to return to Him. Like a good Shepherd, He plays so sweetly on His pipe, that although scarcely hearing it they recognize His call and no longer wander, but return, like lost sheep, to the mansions. So strong is this Pastor’s power over His flock, that they abandon the worldly cares which misled them and enter the castle.” Teresa of Avila, *Interior Castle*, IV.3.1–2, ed. Benedict Zimmerman (London: Thomas Baker, 1930), 71–72.

one who dwells within changes. In both frameworks, moving inward is seen as moving closer to truth, descending not to flee the world but to return to the real. In Bachelard, the chest, the drawer, and the shell all invite not escapism but recollection. They summon memory, gentleness, and the slow unfolding of being. In spiritual language, this is akin to the practice of recollection: the deliberate gathering of the self from distraction towards focused interiority.¹⁹ In this sense, the miniature becomes an icon of the spiritual path not because it represents something else, but because it enacts the movement towards the inner life.

Bachelard's reflections on the "corner" are particularly evocative in this regard. The corner is not a marginal space but a privileged site of withdrawal. It offers a geometry of solitude, a spatial hush where thought gathers, and the soul curls inward like a cat in repose. He writes, "The corner is a haven that ensures us one of the things we prize most highly, immobility."²⁰ This immobility is not stagnation; it is the stillness that allows interior life to rise. In the Christian contemplative traditions, such stillness is a prerequisite for divine encounter. As the Psalmist declares, "Be still, and know that I am God" (Ps. 46:10).

This turn inward is also echoed in Augustine's famous declaration in the *Confessions*: "You were within me, but I was outside myself... I entered into

19 In the *Tercer abecedario espiritual* (1530), the Spanish Franciscan mystic Francisco de Osuna defines "recollection" (or *recogimiento*) as the gathering of the soul inward into its centre, leaving behind external distractions in order to dwell in stillness before God. This interior recollection (*recoger el alma*) is not a mental exercise but a spiritual disposition, "Recollection is also called a reception, for thereby we advance with eager desire, opening wide our heart and emptying it to give place to God," (6,3). The aim is to inhabit what Osuna calls the centre of the soul (*el centro del alma*) where God resides not as an idea but as a living presence. Prayer, in this model, is not discursive but spatial and ontological, a form of dwelling-with that transforms the soul by orienting it toward the divine within. For further reading, especially on how recollection is distinguished from mental discursion see Francisco de Osuna, *The Third Spiritual Alphabet*, 4.5 and 6.1–2, trans. Benedictine of Stanbrook, intro. Father Cuthbert (New York, NY: Benziger Brothers, 1931), 71–75, 96–102. This spatial theology of recollected interiority found echoes throughout the Spanish *siglo de oro*. Bernardino de Laredo would further emphasise the silence and affectivity of *recogimiento*, while Luis de León, Juan de los Angeles, and María de Ágreda each portrayed the soul as a structured inward terrain – a cloister, a garden, or a crystalline sanctuary – where recollection is both a path and a place. Melquiadees Andrés, "La vía espiritual del recogimiento," *Salmanticensis* 20, n. 3 (1973): 655–665. In this sense, *recogimiento* resonates deeply with Bachelard's poetics in which sensory objects are not retreats from reality, but spaces of reverberating presence. Just as Osuna's recollection draws the self inward to the point of divine encounter, Bachelard's reverie draws consciousness into intimate immensity, into a stillness that reveals being by gathering it.

20 Bachelard, *The Poetics of Space*, 137.

my inmost self... and I saw the light that dwells in the heart.”²¹ Augustine’s movement from exterior distraction to interior light is an existential topology Bachelard would recognise. Although not writing within a religious framework, Bachelard charts a similar path of inwardness, one led not by doctrine but by the pull of the poetic image, the small space that calls the self home.

Even the scale of Bachelard’s preferred spaces matters. They are not grand cathedrals or endless deserts, but a cell, a cupboard, or a child’s drawer, places that welcome the body as it is, even the wandering mind or the heart that remembers. They are scaled to care rather than control. In spiritual terms, they are the places where God may be whispered, not thundered (see 1 Kgs 19:11–13). Thus, the inward turn in Bachelard is not a retreat from meaning but a deepening into it. It is a return to the nearness of presence. The soul does not need to climb to heaven or traverse vast theologies to find God. Like the miniature, it needs only to turn inward, to open the drawer or sit in a corner, and dwell in the stillness where presence has already arrived.

Immensity Within: Intimacy and the Infinite

One of the most paradoxical and illuminating aspects of Bachelard’s thought is his treatment of immensity as an experience of the self in intimate spaces. His term “intimate immensity”²² challenges the ordinary polarities of scale. It suggests that vastness is grounded in depth and inwardness, as well as spatial extension. In this way, Bachelard radically reconfigures our understanding of spatial transcendence, opening it to a spiritual interpretation of interior immensity. “Immensity,” he writes, “is within ourselves, attached to a sort of expansion of being that life curbs and caution arrests, but which starts again when we are alone.”²³ This ‘expansion of being’ is not linear or quantitative; it is qualitative. The vastness encountered in the experience of reverie, or in the

21 Albert Cutler’s translation reads, “Belatedly I loved thee, O Beauty so ancient and so new, belatedly I loved thee. For see, thou wast within and I was without, and I sought thee out there. Unlovely, I rushed heedlessly among the lovely things thou hast made. Thou wast with me, but I was not with thee. These things kept me far from thee; even though they were not at all unless they were in thee. Thou didst call and cry aloud, and didst force open my deafness. Thou didst gleam and shine, and didst chase away my blindness. Thou didst breathe fragrant odors and I drew in my breath; and now I pant for thee. I tasted, and now I hunger and thirst. Thou didst touch me, and I burned for thy peace.” Augustine, *Confessions*, X:27, trans. Albert C. Cutler (Philadelphia, PA: The Westminster Press, 1955), 224.

22 Bachelard, *The Poetics of Space*, 183.

23 Bachelard, *The Poetics of Space*, 184.

contemplation of a miniature, is of a different order than the expanses of maps or galaxies. It is existential and, hence, immeasurable. This vision resonates profoundly with the mystical tradition, which likewise locates the infinite in the depth of presence rather than in height or scale. Consider again Julian of Norwich, whose vision of a hazelnut contains perhaps the most condensed image of Bachelard's intimate immensity. The hazelnut, she says, is the entire cosmos preserved in being because God loves it. The soul, in beholding the tiny object, is not drawn into abstraction but into a dense, loving immediacy. Julian, moving away from reflecting on the world's mechanics, enters into hiddenness. Like Bachelard's shells or nests, the hazelnut becomes a vessel for the unspeakably vast because it is so very small. It is in the miniature that mystery concentrates.

This phenomenon is both ontological and poetic. The miniature reveals the world not as it is constructed but as it is lived: enfolded, layered, and revealed slowly. Just as the mystic does not perceive the divine as a concept but as a presence, so too Bachelard does not analyse immensity; he dwells in it. And the place where he finds it most reliably is in intimacy. Perplexingly, immensity becomes spiritual not because it is limitless but because it is inhabitable, personal, and resonant. It opens the soul without overwhelming it. Bachelard's reflections on distance reinforce this point. When he describes a village seen from a high tower or a toy boat drifting on a pond, he notes that smallness itself can produce a reverie of immensity. There is no contradiction. The small expands when seen from a loving distance.²⁴ In theological language, we might say this is the paradox of kenosis. The divine empties itself into smallness; the child in the manger contains the fullness of divinity. For Bachelard, this kenotic logic is spatial: the very structure of immensity may be discovered in the humblest of forms.

There is also an affective dimension to this experience. Bachelard's immensity is not cold or abstract. Instead, it is warm, gentle, and enveloping. He frequently associates it with childhood, with the sensation of being safely enclosed yet imaginatively unbounded.²⁵ This paradox of being enclosed yet open mirrors the mystical language of dwelling in God who is both infinitely beyond and intimately within, a God who can be touched in silence and approached in stillness. It is no wonder that mystics often speak of God as a shelter, a rock, a

24 Bachelard, *The Poetics of Space*, 24, 139, 173.

25 Bachelard, *The Poetics of Space*, 28, 65, 132, 169.

cleft, or a hidden chamber. These metaphors are spatialisations of intimacy that paradoxically reveal the infinite. Bachelard's image of the "nest" is emblematic in this sense. The nest is at once protective and open. It is the place of beginning, warmth, and return.²⁶ In theological terms, one might find parallels in Marian imagery. Mary is the nest of the Incarnate Word, the space that holds and shelters the immensity of God. But the nest is also an image of the human soul, a space prepared for presence, receptive to flight and return. In Bachelard's hands, it becomes a tender symbol of ontological hospitality.

Ultimately, Bachelard's treatment of immensity does not take us into the sky but into the depths of dwelling. Immensity is not the destination of a journey but the deepening of a room, the silence in a drawer, the breath within a shell. His is a phenomenology of scale turned inward, a spatial mysticism without religion but not without resonance. When Bachelard writes, "The poetic image places us at the origin of the speaking being,"²⁷ he gestures towards a space where poetry and prayer touch. It is the place where the soul speaks inwardly toward that which exceeds it yet already inhabits it.²⁸ In this way, immensity is not out there but right here and right now, folded into the miniature and disclosed in the dwelling, perceived not with our eyes alone but with our whole being. Such is Bachelard's spiritual topology, a dwelling place of presence.

Spiritual Uses of Language: Poetic and Mystical Speech

If Bachelard's phenomenology of space offers a spiritual sensibility, then his approach to language forms one of its most vital organs. He does not treat language as a transparent vehicle for transmitting mere information nor as a tool of conceptual clarity. For Bachelard, poetic language is revelatory. It speaks being into resonance. His poetics, therefore, is not merely stylistic, but ontological. And it is in this understanding of language that his vision draws most closely to the mystical traditions, which likewise prize speech as evocation, invocation, and sometimes even abdication in the face of presence.

In Bachelard, poetic language is a mode of being, not a mode of saying. It awakens rather than informs. For instance, the miniature is never simply

26 Bachelard, *The Poetics of Space*, 52, 93, 96, 99–100, 103.

27 Bachelard, *The Poetics of Space*, xxiii.

28 He explains, "Because of its novelty and its action, the poetic image has an entity and a dynamism of its own; it is referable to a direct ontology. This ontology is what I plan to study." Bachelard, *The Poetics of Space*, xvi.

described in *The Poetics of Space*; it is made to resonate. A drawer is not just wooden and square; it is secret and warm, a world within a world, a retreat for memory.²⁹ A word like ‘nest’ is not a symbol of safety; it evokes safety with such fullness that it gathers the reader into the very sensation of being held. In this, Bachelard joins the mystics who use language to generate presence and gesture beyond what can be said, attempting to hold what cannot be grasped. One might compare his poetic reverie to the Christian practice of *lectio divina*, in which Scripture is read not for exegetical content but for intimate dwelling. The aim is to linger or ruminate, to allow a phrase or word to shimmer in the mind and the heart.³⁰ As Bachelard writes of the poetic image:

The poetic image is an emergence from language; it is always a little above the language of signification. By living the poems we read, we have then the salutary experience of emerging. This, no doubt, is emerging at short range. But these acts of emergence are repeated; poetry puts language in a state of emergence, in which life becomes manifest through its vivacity. These linguistic impulses, which stand out from the ordinary rank of pragmatic language, are miniatures of the vital impulse. A micro-Bergsonism that abandoned the thesis of language-as-instrument in favor of the thesis of language-as-reality would find in poetry numerous documents on the intense life of language.³¹

29 Bachelard, *The Poetics of Space*, 78.

30 Guigo II explains this practice, “Reading is the careful study of the Scriptures, concentrating all one’s powers on it. Meditation is the busy application of the mind to seek with the help of one’s own reason for knowledge of hidden truth. Prayer is the heart’s devoted turning to God to drive away evil and obtain what is good. Contemplation is when the mind is in some sort lifted up to God and held above itself, so that it tastes the joys of everlasting sweetness. [...] Reading seeks for the sweetness of a blessed life, meditation perceives it, prayer asks for it, contemplation tastes it.” Guigo II, *The Ladder of Monks: A Letter on the Contemplative Life*, II-III, trans. Edmund Colledge and James Walsh (Kalamazoo, MI: Cistercian Publications, 1981), 68–69. This contemplative relationship to language – where a word is not interpreted but inhabited – has deep resonances with other mystical traditions. In Sufism, the practice of *dhikr*, or remembrance, involves the rhythmic repetition of divine names or Qur’anic phrases not to gain information, but to cultivate presence. As the heart repeats the Name, it becomes a dwelling-place for the One named. Like *lectio divina*, *dhikr* transforms the practitioner not through concept, but through attunement, inviting the soul to rest in the space that language opens rather than closes. William C. Chittick, *The Sufi Path of Knowledge: Ibn al-‘Arabi’s Metaphysics of Imagination* (Albany, NY: State University of New York Press, 1989), 62–63, 356–358.

31 Bachelard, *The Poetics of Space*, xxvii.

Likewise, in *lectio divina*, the text becomes an inhabitable space, an inner world that surrounds and transforms the reader. This attentive reading is an interiorised language, just as Bachelard's phenomenology is an interiorised experience of space.

Mystical speech is always aware of its limits. It dances near silence. For instance, *The Cloud of Unknowing* insists that God is not to be reached by thought but by a blind stirring of love.³² In the Sanskrit tradition, the Brihadaranyaka Upanishad uses "neti neti" (not this, not that) to express the inaccessibility of the Ultimate to conceptual grasp. The highest Reality or Truth cannot be said, only unsaid; it is approached not by definition, but by releasing all definitions.³³ In such texts, language functions less to delimit meaning than to allow it to unfold, creating space for a deeper mode of understanding. Bachelard's use of poetic citations works in a similar way: rather than supporting an argument, these fragments invite entry. In *The Poetics of Space*, a phrase from Miłosz, Supervielle or Baudelaire is not offered as proof but as a threshold, so that the reader may cross it and allow the image itself to act. In this sense, language resembles prayer, a doorway rather than a demonstration.

There is also a reverence in Bachelard's prose that evokes a liturgical tone. His repetitions and gentle refrains – e.g., "the poetic imagination" and "in the presence of"³⁴ – mimic the rhythms of chant or mantra. These are not rhetorical flourishes. They are techniques of temporal slowing; they hold the reader in space and delay the rush to closure. In this sense, Bachelard performs spiritual space rather than simply describing it. He structures time around attention. He creates, in language, the very rhythm of reverie he seeks to evoke.

To this, one might add his emphasis on naming. The power of naming in *The Poetics of Space* is intimate. To name a space (the attic, the cellar, the corner) is a relational act, a calling forth of a particular quality of being. In

32 *The Cloud of Unknowing*, 3, 4, 6, ed. Justin McCann (New York, NY: Benziger Brothers, 1924), 11, 15, 24.

33 Verse 2.3.6 reads, "The form of that 'being' is as follows: Like a cloth dyed with turmeric, or like grey sheep's wool, or like the (scarlet) insect called Indragopa, or like a tongue of fire, or like a white lotus, or like a flash of lightning. He who knows it as such attains splendour like a flash of lightning. Now therefore the description (of Brahman): 'Not this, not this.' Because there is no other and more appropriate description than this 'Not this.' Now Its name: 'The Truth of truth.' The vital force is truth, and It is the Truth of that." *The Brihadaranyaka Upanishad: With the Commentary of Shankaracharya*, trans. Swami Madhavananda (Mayavati, Himalayas: Advaita Ashrama, 1950), 336–337.

34 Bachelard, *The Poetics of Space*, xv, xix, xxiii, xxvii, xxviii, xxxv, 152, 157, 167, 186, 189, 199, 204, 225, 227, 239.

spiritual traditions, naming often carries sacramental weight. For instance, in the Judeo-Christian tradition, in God's self-disclosure to Moses in the burning bush (Ex. 3:14) or in Christ's naming of Mary of Magdala in the garden after the resurrection (Jn 20:16), the name becomes a site of recognition and, thus, transformation. For Bachelard, poetic names do something similar. They re-enchant the world and call space into presence. Yet, as in the mystics, there is in Bachelard a humility before silence. Reverie does not lead to closure. So, the poetic image, like the divine name, remains open, resisting exhaustion and inviting return. It is perhaps the most spiritual dimension of Bachelard's language: its refusal to master. The image does not end in knowledge but in dwelling. The drawer is never emptied, the shell never fully opened. Something remains hidden.³⁵

Thus, in Bachelard, language is neither ornamental nor explanatory but spatial. It is a room the soul enters, a shelter for being, a resonance chamber for silence. In this way, his phenomenology offers a poetics of attention not unlike prayer. To speak the world gently, attentively, and poetically is to bless it. It is to draw near to its essence. It is to say, in the deepest sense: Here. I am listening.

Toward a Spiritual Phenomenology of Space

To speak of a spiritual phenomenology of space, then, is to articulate a mode of attention that moves through four key dynamics: stillness, depth, interiority, and imaginative dwelling. These are not new concepts in mystical thought, but Bachelard presents them without doctrinal framing, inviting even secular consciousness into a contemplative posture.

35 Pavel Florensky, a twentieth-century scientist turned theologian from the Russian Orthodox tradition, holds a similar idea about Truth. Florensky's greatest concern was to seek how, on the basis of conditioned human knowledge, one could come to know a Truth that was fundamentally comprehensible and not illusory or constructed. His conclusion was that there must be a Truth that is self-proving – “life itself” – which is “reachable” and which underpins all things and circumstances. If the Truth exists and if it is to be credible, it must be self-proving. It must provide the necessary grounds for its existence, it must leave its traces in creation and the necessary inner laws by which to discover it, and it must guarantee that within the entropic and fluid conditions of space and time lies an ectropic reality discoverable not rationally (*рассудочный*) but reasonably and contemplatively (*разумий*). Pavel Florensky, *The Pillar and Ground of the Truth: An Essay in Orthodox Theodicy in Twelve Letters*, trans. Boris Jakim, intro. Richard Gustafson (Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press, 1997), 14–38; Glen Attard, *Closest to the Heart: A Mystagogy of Spiritual Friendship in Pavel Florenskij's 'The Pillar and Ground of the Truth,'* foreword by Robert Slesinski, afterword by Avril Pyman (Malta: Horizons, 2020), 60, 148.

1. Stillness as Spatial Disposition: Bachelard's favoured spaces – corners, nests, drawers, shells – are not places of movement but of rest. They are chambers of quiet, pockets of immobility that allow being to settle like dust upon the inner furnishings of the soul. In spiritual traditions, stillness is attentiveness rather than inactivity. The cell of the monk, the silence of *lectio divina*, and the hidden retreat are all spaces where God is heard in the absence of noise. Bachelard gives us a language for this stillness without invoking God: he gives us space as a hush.
2. Depth Over Extension: Rather than seeking God on a vertical scale (in the heavens), mystical traditions often locate the divine in the depths of the soul. Bachelard's emphasis on verticality is downward and inward, a humble cellar rather than a grand spire. His phenomenology values depth over breadth, the kind that opens inward like a spiral. Depth is not an abyss in the existentialist sense, a bottomless void that evokes disorientation or dread, as in Kierkegaard or Heidegger. Rather, it is a nesting space. Bachelard's inwardness is not the terror of the infinite but the intimacy of the hidden. Spiritually, this parallels the move from abstraction to intimacy, from concept to presence, from ontological vertigo to interior hospitality. Depth here is not devouring; it is indwelling.
3. Interiority as Inhabitation: Space, for Bachelard, is not outside of us. It is something we carry, something we enter by remembering, imagining, and returning. In spiritual terms, this is what Augustine calls the interiority of memory in *The Confessions*, what Teresa maps as the mansions of the soul in *The Interior Castle*, and what Eckhart calls the ground of the soul in his *Sermons*. The miniature, in Bachelard's thought, is a key to this interiority because it welcomes the self to return to itself and, in doing so, open up to something greater.
4. Imaginative Dwelling as Prayer: Finally, Bachelard's phenomenology is a practice of dwelling, not in structures but in images, not in explanations but in reveries. This form of imaginative presence is structurally akin to contemplative prayer. Both require slowness and resist mastery. Both trust that what cannot be captured by thought may still be inhabited by love. To dwell in a poetic image is not unlike dwelling in a name of God, in a moment of silence, or in a word from Scripture that shimmers without resolution.

From these dynamics, we may begin to sketch a spiritual phenomenology that is radically attentive and beyond dogma or abstraction. It is grounded in space as relation, asking where presence dwells and what attention would allow that presence to be perceived. Bachelard may not directly contribute to mysticism, but he lends himself to its conditions. He reminds us that our relation to space is formative. How we enter a room, imagine a drawer, or speak a word shapes the space of the soul. In this sense, Bachelard becomes a subtle spiritual teacher, one who teaches postures: the posture of attentiveness, reverence, and nearness. To practice spiritual phenomenology, then, is to reinhabit the world. It is to see space not as empty but as waiting, not as external but as shared. The drawer may be closed, and the shell may be silent, but to the attentive soul, they are invitations, presences. And perhaps, to borrow a final metaphor from Julian of Norwich, they are like that tiny hazelnut: small, held, and burning with the fullness of divine love.

Conclusion: The Tiny as Threshold

In conclusion, in many ways, *The Poetics of Space* is a meditation on how space becomes place through intimacy and imagination. In doing so, it perhaps unintentionally opens itself to spiritual interpretation. Though Bachelard never writes as a theologian, his attention to presence, interiority, stillness, and dwelling resonates deeply with spiritual and mystical traditions. From this angle, the present paper has sought to engage Bachelard anew, not to reduce him to an unwitting theologian, but to recognise in his poetics of space a spiritual topology, a way of imagining being that moves through contraction, presence, and reverent interiority.

Reading *The Poetics of Space* through the lens of spiritual attentiveness, we have found in Bachelard a phenomenologist of more than the poetic image. Quietly, he is a thinker of the sacred, a dwelling presence that fills the intimate spaces of life. His meditation on miniature spaces becomes a kind of secular scripture for the contemplative imagination. These spaces are not ornaments of reverie; they are thresholds. Thresholds to what? To presence. To attention. To the quiet saturation of being that mystics have long recognised as the atmosphere in which God dwells. For Bachelard, the miniature is not a retreat from reality but a deepening into it. It allows us to grasp the immensity of the world from within the shelter of the small. It also allows the soul to turn inward in hospitality, making space within for that which is beyond us.

Throughout this paper, we have explored how Bachelard's phenomenology aligns with spiritual traditions that locate transcendence in interiority. The stillness of the corner, the soft enclosure of the nest, and the evocative silence of a poetic word are potential sites of contemplation and of a spiritual topography of dwelling. From Julian's hazelnut to Teresa's inner castle, from Augustine's recollection to the *Cloud's* unknowing, the Christian mystical tradition has long dwelt in spaces of inward immensity. Bachelard offers no theology of these spaces, but his phenomenology provides a language through which we might perceive them anew. More importantly, Bachelard's vision invites us to see the world again as presence to be received rather than as a resource. He teaches us to reverence space, to pause before it, to let it speak, not far from what the mystics describe as contemplative prayer, where God is permitted to be acknowledged as present. Not storming heaven but finding it already burning quietly in a child's toy box, in the shell cupped in the palm, in the silence between words.

If there is a spiritual phenomenology of the miniature, it begins here, in the patient recovery of the world as a gift. In a time dominated by the large, the fast, and the external, Bachelard's vision reminds us that the infinite may still be curled within the finite and that the soul, when small enough, may find space to dwell. The tiny, then, is not an endpoint. It is a divide and a place of crossing. Through it, we may rediscover the vast interior terrains of presence, reverie, and divine nearness. And perhaps, in learning to dwell with care in the miniature, we may begin to dwell again with God, with the world, and with one another.

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